

Classical Newar Annotation Manual

Part I - Preprocessing

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Version control

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Part I: Pre-processing

This part of the manual explains the preprocessing procedures employed for the Classical Newar corpus to prepare it for segmentation, POS tagging, parsing, and information structural annotation. This stage involves several steps: **describing the corpus**, outlining the **workflows** and tools used, our decisions on the **representation of Classical Newar**, and converting handwritten or printed text into machine-readable format through **OCR** (optical character recognition) and **HTR** (handwritten text recognition) with Transkribus. It also includes **cleaning editorial conventions** to standardise the text and **normalising variant spellings** to ensure consistency. These preprocessing steps are essential for accurate segmentation and subsequent linguistic analysis.

Note that throughout these Classical Newar annotations manuals references may be made to what is done in the Classical Tibetan situation. This is because this manual is being developed in parallel to a similar manual for Classical Tibetan. These references are retained for ease of reference upon the date of the publication of the Classical Tibetan manual.

1. Description of Corpus

There is no prior digital corpus of Classical Newar texts, unlike other major Central and South Asian languages such as Classical Tibetan, Sanskrit, or Buddhist Chinese. Starting with **diplomatically edited** texts allows for greater efficiency, enabling the development of segmenters and POS taggers to expedite processing. **Narrative literature** is prioritised to quickly identify linguistically interesting data due to its variety of verb forms and reported speech. Texts from each century of Classical Newar literature (12th–19th C.) were selected to study diachronic changes. The corpus mainly consists of **story collections** reflecting the spoken language. Text processing was **prioritised based on their editorial status**, starting with Romanised or Devanāgarī editions.

Regarding texts that have already been annotated and prioritised, the *Ukū Bāhāḥ Palmleaf* (1114 CE) was included as a representative of early Newar literature, revealing significant differences from later texts and requiring manual POS tagging. The *Gopālarājavaṃśāvalī* (1259–1380 CE) was similarly processed. From the later strata, which will make up the most relevant chunk of the corpus, the *Vetālapaṅcaviṃśati* (1675 CE) was annotated using Felix Otter's diplomatic transcription and grammatical analyses. The more recent *Maṇicūḍāvādānoddhṛta* (19th century) provided chronological breadth and Buddhist material. Future phases will incorporate other edited Classical Newar texts and manuscripts using HTR models, including bilingual translations. For more details, including a chart of selected texts, see O'Neill & Meelen (2024, §3).

2. Workflows

In order to create the fully-annotated corpus from scratch, we developed a three-phased pipeline starting with Preprocessing, followed by word and sentence Segmentation and Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging and, finally, annotation of syntax, semantics and information structure. The first phase can include digitalisation processes (OCR or HTR) where necessary, but always includes a stage of cleaning, formatting and normalisation of the text to prepare it for downstream processing. This results in normalised texts that can be fed into NLP tools for further annotation. The second phase is focused on splitting the text into words and sentences, as well as adding detailed morphosyntactic information in the form of Part-of-Speech (POS) tags. The automatically generated annotation is then manually corrected to ensure the best results for the final stage of deep annotation in which words are combined into hierarchical phrases to create syntactic constituents, as well as features that indicate

semantic (e.g. animacy, volitionality of verbs) and pragmatic/information-structural properties such as topic and focus. These layers of annotation are also added in a semi-supervised way with a final round of manual correction to ensure the results are ready for linguistic querying. A detailed overview of the first and second phase of this pipeline is discussed in O'Neill & Meelen (2024); Phase 3 'Syntax & Information Structure (IS)' will be discussed in detail in Meelen & O'Neill (2024, §2).

3. Representation of Classical Newar

The corpus **transliterates Pracalit and Devanāgarī transcriptions to IAST transliterations** using free script converters like Aksharamukha. Indologists have preferred the IAST transliteration scheme for the past century despite various transcription approaches for Newar, such as Jørgensen's scheme, which distinguished between pronunciations not indicated by Devanāgarī or Pracalit orthography. These conventions, based on speculations about pronunciation, are impractical for OCR or HTR. Recent practices by Malla (2000) and Otter (2020) **retain the final inherent -a to reflect manuscript orthography**. Moreover, IAST transliteration is optimal for the Classical Newar corpus, especially for bilingual Sanskrit-Newar texts, as it ensures consistency and reversibility using converters like Aksharamukha. Therefore, **the corpus employs a strictly diplomatic IAST transliteration of Pracalit and Devanāgarī transcriptions and adaptation of non-diplomatic transliterations (e.g. Jørgensen & Leinhard) to IAST conventions**. For more details, see O'Neill & Meelen (2024, §4).

4. Text Recognition

a. OCR transcribed PDFs

Texts in Devanāgarī or Latin script are digitised **using Tesseract 5 with the gImageReader frontend** and the **Sanskrit IAST Trainddata** (Kumar 2021) or Tesseract's native **Devanāgarī Trainddata**. For installation instructions, see [here](#). Depending on the quality of the image, **Google Lens OCR** may become increasingly effective for future OCR requirements. On correcting OCR errors, see O'Neill & Meelen (2024, §4.2.5)

b. Transcribe with Transkribus

The corpus uses an HTR model for transcribing Pracalit into Pracalit Unicode using Transkribus, named **"Pracalit for Sanskrit and Newar MSS 16th to 19th C."** This PyLaia model is based on transcriptions of four Nepalese manuscripts. The model, trained on 441 pages and validated on 242 pages, is designed for scriptio continua texts and does not recognise spacing. With a character error rate of 2.6% on the training set and 0.1% on the validation set, it can be refined further (when using, check for new versions). It can serve as a **base model for quickly training new models** with fewer folia. See O'Neill & Hill (2022) and O'Neill & Meelen (2024) for more details.

5. Cleaning editorial conventions

The extent to which editorial conventions need to be cleaned depends on whether we are working with a previously edited text. If so, we need to de-edit the text to make it appear more representative of a diplomatic edition. To ensure the completeness of words and maintain the integrity of pagination and folio numbers, we **reunify words split by folio breaks** in our corpus. **Split words are rejoined and marked with an asterisk** to indicate deviation from the original manuscript. For examples, see O'Neill & Meelen (2024, §4.2.2).

Regarding editors' variants, **remove dashes** that break up compounds and **accept editor's variants as the best versions, marking these emendations with asterisks before the words. For corrupted forms, place the asterisk before the words. Light corrections of errors are marked with double asterisks.** See O'Neill & Meelen (2024, §4.2.3).

6. Normalisation

For normalisation, we **reintroduce the final inherent -a** in Classical Newar texts, where it has been removed to align with contemporary pronunciation. Additionally, we standardise orthography in Romanised texts to ensure consistency. Where they have been placed before consonants, **adjust the placement of aspiration markers to match current transliteration schemes by moving them after their consonants** (e.g., change **hñ** to **ñh**), but **retain them before y** (e.g., **hy**). These steps ensure the texts retain their original orthography while providing consistent formatting for the subsequent steps.